

METHODOLOGICAL AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LEXICAL UNITS

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Abstract: Lexical units referred to as syntactic atoms, can be independent such as in the case of root words or parts of compound words or they require association with other units, as prefixes and suffixes do. The former are termed free morphemes and the latter bound morphemes.

Keywords: lexical unit, suffixes, nouns, adjectives, science, terminology, systematics, clarity.

INTRODUCTION. Something that is lexical is related to words. A dictionary is lexical, as is a tongue-twister! Lexicon is a fancy word for a dictionary. The word lexical is an adjective that describes anything that pertains to words or vocabulary, or to even language more generally. Solving a crossword puzzle is a lexical activity. Lexical unit is a division in the sense of a lexeme. For e.g. If the two meanings of a word are related, then they are lexical units of one lexeme. A lexeme is the term used in Linguistics to refer to a minimal unit of language. Lexical Semantics deconstruct words and phrases within a line of text to understand the meaning in terms of context. Lexicon is mental dictionary which stores lexemes or senses or both. Example: The word Bank can mean the side of river or can mean at money vaults.

METHODOLOGY.

Various authors have argued that a language's vocabulary is chaotic rather than organized, in contrast to grammar. Nevertheless, given current research in language theory, we are now able to organize this "chaos" somewhat.

Lexicology examines the recurring patterns in semantic linkages as well as any formal methods that may be used to express them in phonological, morphological, or contextual contexts.

It seeks to organize things. Recently, there has been a lot of discussion on various issues related to the systematic character of language vocabulary, both domestically and internationally. Based on some dialectics and its teaching of the general interconnectedness and interconnection of phenomena in nature and society, Some scholars are now approaching a satisfactory solution. Here are a few crucial aspects that need to be mentioned. In modern lexicology, the term "system" refers to a collection of components that are related to one another and operate as a unit under certain rules, rather than just the totality of English vocabulary. It is made up of interdependent parts of the same order that are connected in certain, precise ways to form a coherent, homogenous whole. Furthermore, a language's vocabulary is an adaptive system that is always modifying itself to fit the ever changing

demands and circumstances of intercultural communication and the real world. It keeps evolving by resolving conflicts between its current state and the new requirements and tasks it must fulfill. According to abstract set theory, a set is a group of separate, definite objects that may be thought of as a whole. Because an object in a set may be identified from the other elements even though it is unlikely to emerge again, a set is defined as a collection of distinct elements. When there are more items in a set than there are rules that may be used to construct them, the set is said to be structured. A set can be expressed by declaring its distinguishing trait or by specifying, or listing, every element in the set. For instance, the elements *the*, *a/an*, and *zero* may be defined as belonging to the closed set of English articles. Conversely, the set of English compounds is unlimited (open), comprising all words with two or more stems that are found in the language as free forms.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS. Every epoch's lexicon includes productive aspects typical of that era, others that are becoming less common and outdated, and, lastly, certain novel events that serve as important indicators of emerging patterns for epochs to come. The current state of a system is abstraction, akin to science fiction that can occasionally help with linguistic research, but the language's actual system is always evolving. By identifying the characteristics of its constituent parts, the various contrasts and similarities that exist between them inside a language, and the manner in which they are impacted by extralinguistic reality, lexicology investigates this whole. The connections between words and the aspects of objective reality they serve to represent, as well as their reliance on the social, cognitive, and cultural evolution of the language community, are referred to as extra-linguistic linkages. Our methodological foundation is based on The phrase used by V.V. Vinogradov encompasses the totality of words and expressions as well as the functional and derivational patterns of word forms and word groups, semantic clusters, and word relationships. The following can be used to illustrate how different layers of the language system interact in English. The monomorphemic analytic nature of the English language and the lack of morphological means are closely related to the widespread development of homonymy and polysemy, the loss of motivation, the abundance of generic words, and the relatively limited autonomy of English words in comparison to Russian words. All of them in turn are caused by mechanisms that are definitely related to leveling and losing endings, at least in part.

DISCUSSION. The term system as applied to vocabulary should not be understood to mean a well-defined or rigid system. As it has been stated above it is an adaptive system and cannot be completely and exactly characterised by deterministic functions; that is for the present state of science it is not possible to specify the system's entire future by its status at some one instant of its operation. In other words, the vocabulary is not simply a probabilistic system but a set of interrelated adaptive subsystems.

An approximation is always made possible by leaving some things out of account. But we have to remember that the rules of language are mostly analogies.

The following simple example offered by J. Lyons illustrates this point: the regular, that is statistically predominant, pattern for adjective stems is to form abstract nouns by means of the suffix *-ness*: *shortness*, *narrowness*, *shallowness*. All the antonyms of the above-mentioned words, however, follow a different pattern: they have a dental suffix: *length*, *width*, *depth*. This second analogy becomes a constraint on the working of the first. Moreover, the relationship of the adjective *big* with the rest of the system is even more unpredictable, as it is mostly correlated with the noun *size*. The semantic correlation then is as follows:

short = narrow = shallow = long = wide = deep = big shortness narrowness shallowness length width depth size.

At this point it will be helpful to remember that it is precisely the most frequent words that

show irregular or suppletive derivation and inflection.

Last but not least, one final point may be made about the lexical system, namely that its elements are characterised by their combinatorial and contrastive properties determining their syntagmatic and paradigmatic relationships. A word enters into syntagmatic (linear) combinatorial relationships with other lexical units that can form its context, serving to identify and distinguish its meaning. Lexical units are known to be context-dependent. E. g. in *the hat on her head* the noun *head* means ‘part of the body’, whereas in *the head of the department* *Head* means ‘chief. A word enters into contrastive paradigmatic relations with all other words, e. g. *head, chief, director*, etc. that can occur in the same context and be contrasted to it.¹ This principle of contrast or opposition is fundamental in modern linguistics and we shall deal with it at length in § 1.6. concerned with the theory of oppositions.

Paradigmatic and syntagmatic studies of meaning are functional because the meaning of the lexical unit is studied first not through its relation to referent but through its functions in relation to other units.

Functional approach is contrasted to referential or onomasiological approach, otherwise called theory of nomination, in which meaning is studied as the interdependence between words and their referents, that is things or concepts they name, i.e. various names given to the same sense. The onomasiological study of lexical units became especially prominent in the last two decades. The revival of interest in onomasiological matters is reflected in a large volume of publications on the subject. An outline of the main trends of current research will be found in the monographs on the Theory of Nomination issued by the Institute of Linguistics of the Academy of Sciences.

The study of the lexical system must also include the study of the words’ combinatorial possibilities — their capacity to combine with one another in groups of certain patterns, which serve to identify meanings. Most modern research in linguistics attaches great importance to what is variously called valency, distributional characteristics, colligation and collocation, combining power or otherwise. This research shows that combinatorial possibilities of words play an important part in almost every lexicological issue.

Syntagmatic relationships being based on the linear character of speech are studied by means of contextual, valency, distributional, transformational and some other types of analysis. Paradigmatic linguistic relationships determining the vocabulary system are based on the interdependence of words within the vocabulary (synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, etc.). Diachronically the interdependence of words within the lexical subsystem may be seen by observing shifts in the meaning of existing words that occur when a new word is introduced into their semantic sphere. This interdependence is one of the reasons why historical linguistics can never achieve any valuable results if it observes only the development of isolated words. Almost any change in one word will cause changes in one or several other words. Characteristic examples are to be found in the influence of borrowings upon native words. The native OE *haerfest* (ModE *harvest* || Germ *Herbst*) originally meant not only the gathering of grain’ but also ‘the season for reaping’. Beginning with the end of the 14th century, that is after the Romance word *autumne* > *autumn* was borrowed, the second meaning in the native word was lost and transferred to the word *autumn*.

When speaking about the influence of other aspects on the development of the vocabulary, we mean the phonetical, morphological and syntactical systems of the English language as they condition the sound form, morphological structure, motivation and meaning of words. This influence is manifold, and we shall have to limit our illustration to the most elementary examples. The monosyllabic phonological type of the English word, for instance, enhances homonymy. Cf. *miss* v ‘not hit’, ‘not catch’ and *miss* n — a title for a girl or unmarried

woman.

The influence of morphology is manifest, for instance, in the development of non-affixed word-formation. Cf. *harvest* n and *harvest* v.

The above considerations are not meant to be exhaustive; they are there to give some general idea of the relationships in question.

In this connection it is necessary to point out that various interpretations of the same linguistic phenomena have repeatedly been offered and have even proved valuable for their respective purposes, just as in other sciences various interpretations may be given for the same facts of reality in conformity with this or that practical task. To be scientific, however, these interpretations cannot be arbitrary: they must explain facts and permit explanation and prediction of other facts. Therefore they must fit without bringing contradictions into the whole system of the theory created for the subject.

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